

Synthesis of 3-Arylimino-5-Substituted-1,2,4-Dithiazoles. Part II: Oxidative Debenzylation and Cyclisation of S-Benzyliso-N-Arylthiocarbamoyl- phenylthioacetamides

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A series of new 3-arylimino-5-benzyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles has been synthesised by the oxidative debenzylation and cyclisation of S-benzyliso-N-arylthiocarbamoylphenylthioacetamides with bromine in concentrated chloroform solution. These compounds have been characterised by the direct oxidation of the corresponding-N-arylthiocarbamoylphenylthioacetamides and also by i.r. spectral studies. The mechanism of the reaction has been proposed.

THE facile oxidative debenzylation and cyclisation in the isothioacetamide system leading to the formation of the substituted 1,2,4-dithiazoles¹ led us to extend the reaction to synthesise certain hitherto unknown 3-arylimino-5-benzyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles. In the present communication, we report the preparation of certain S-benzyliso-N-arylthiocarbamoyl phenylthioacetamides (II) and their oxidative debenzylation and cyclisation to the corresponding 3-arylimino-5-benzyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles (IV).

Phenylthioacetamide, obtained by the thiohydrolysis of benzylcyanide, was benzylated with benzylchloride in methanol in presence of sodium methoxide, and the resultant S-benzyliso-phenylthioacetamide (I) was condensed with appropriate arylisothiocyanate to afford phenylthioacetamides (II). The chloroform solution of the latter was then treated with bromine, when the benzyl group of these was eliminated as benzylbromide followed by ring closure to the related 3-arylimino-5-benzyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles (IV). These have also been obtained by the oxidation of the related N-arylthiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamides (III) which were obtained by the reductive debenzylation of the related S-benzyliso-N-arylthiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamides (II) with hydrogen sulphide in pyridine-triethylamine² and also by the reduction of (IV) under identical conditions. In all the cases, the structures of the compounds (III) and (IV) were confirmed by their synthesis through alternative routes as described above.

The IR spectra of compounds (II) and (III) showed characteristic absorptions in the region around 3150–3400 cm⁻¹ and 1470–1500 cm⁻¹ indicating -NH stretching^{3,4} and N-C(=S)-N-grouping⁴. A weak absorption in the region 1600–1640 and strong absorption at 1250 cm⁻¹ were recorded due to N-H⁴ and C-NHAr⁴ deformational vibrations of compounds (II) and (III). Compounds (IV) were characterised by the

absorptions recorded at 1620s (-C=N-grouping)^{5,6} 1350–1500 (ring stretching)⁴, and 485–510w (-S-S-linkage)^{5,6} respectively.

The Scheme of reaction can be represented as follows:

where R = phenyl-, *p*-tolyl-, *p*-chlorophenyl-, *p*-methoxyphenyl-, *m*-chlorophenyl-, and benzyl groups.
bz = benzyl group, and ph = Phenyl group.

Mechanism:

The initial step appears to be the attack of oxidant (bromine) on the sulphur atom of the C=S group in isothiocarbamoylthioamide (II). This sulphur of the thiocarbamoyl group is a strong nucleophile (R-NH-C=S ↔ R-NH=C-S) and offers a suitable site for attack by an electrophilic reagent such as Br⁺ available

from the oxidant, forming a sulphenyl bromide type intermediate (V) which eliminates benzylbromide and forms a dithiazole Salt (IV). Thus :

tion of excess of benzene afforded the desired *S*-benzyliso-phenylthioacetamide, (4.15 g, 52%), m.p. 49°, (ethanol).

S-Benzyliso-*N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamides (II): The details of a typical experiment are as follows:

S-Benzyliso-phenylthioacetamide (5g) was refluxed with phenylisothiocyanate (2.8g) and 25 ml of sodium hydroxide (10%) for 1 hr. The resulting mixture was extracted with benzene which was further refluxed for one hour. on evaporation of the solvent was obtained the expected *S*-benzyliso-*N*-phenylthiocarbamoylphenylthioacetamide (II), which was finally crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 148°. (yield 2.81 g, 36%). All the thioacetamides prepared are shown in Table 1.

3-Arylimino-5-benzyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles (IV) :

(i) Oxidative debenzylation and cyclisation of *S*-benzyliso-*N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamide (II). Details of a typical experiment are as follows :

To *S*-benzyliso-*N*-phenylthiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamide (7g), moistened with little chloroform (2 ml), was added bromine (1 ml) in small portions with vigorous stirring. Debenzylation was evident from the evolution of the lachrymatory fumes of benzylbromide. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 30 min. and then it was washed with ether. Treatment of resulting mass with ethanol afforded the desired 3-phenylimino-5-benzyl-1,2,4-dithiazole hydrobromide, which on basification with ammonia gave the corresponding free base. This was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 155°C, (yield 3g, 58%). The results are given in Table 2.

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded in Nujol on a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer (Model 720).

S-Benzyliso-phenylthioacetamide (I) : Phenylthioacetamide (5g) was benzylated with benzyl chloride (4.2g) in methanol (25 ml) in presence of sodium methoxide (2g). The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 hr. and was allowed to stand overnight. It was then refluxed for about 15 min. Solvent was evaporated at reduced pressure, and resulting product extracted with benzene and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evapora-

TABLE 1—*S*-BENZYLISO-*N*-ARYLTHIOCARBAMOYL-PHENYLTHIOACETAMIDES (II)

Reactants	<i>S</i> -benzyliso- <i>N</i> -arylthiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamides formed	Molecular Formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Analysis	
					Found	Reqd.
BT + Phenylisothiocyanate	<i>S</i> -Benzyliso- <i>N</i> -phenyl-TT	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$	148	36	C : 69.85 H : 5.26	70.21 5.31
BT + <i>p</i> -tolylisothiocyanate	<i>S</i> -Benzyliso- <i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -tolyl-TT	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$	176	40	N : 7.34 S : 16.80	7.18 16.41
BT + <i>p</i> -Chlorophenylisothiocyanate	<i>S</i> -Benzyliso- <i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-TT	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{Cl}$	172	33	N : 6.98 S : 16.02	6.82 15.59
BT + <i>p</i> -methoxyphenylisothiocyanate	<i>S</i> -Benzyliso- <i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl-TT	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$	194	38	N : 7.04 S : 15.90	6.89 15.77
BT + <i>m</i> -Chlorophenylisothiocyanate	<i>S</i> -Benzyliso- <i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl-TT	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{Cl}$	102	25	C : 64.58 H : 4.63	64.31 4.52
BT + Benzylisothiocyanate	<i>S</i> -Benzyliso- <i>N</i> -benzyl-TT	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$	145	43	C : 71.04 H : 5.78	70.76 5.64

BT denotes - *S*-Benzyliso-phenylthioacetamide
TT denotes - Thiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamide.

TABLE 2—3-ARYLIMINO-5-BENZYL-1,2,4-DITHIAZOLES (IV)

Reactants	3-arylimino-5-benzyl-1,2,4-dithiazole formed	Molecular Formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Analysis	
					Found	Reqd.
S-Benzyliso-N-phenyl-TT	3-phenylimino-5-benzyl-D	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂	155	58	N : 9.82 S : 22.76	9.86 22.54
S-Benzyliso-N-p-tolyl-TT	3-p-tolylimino-5-benzyl-D	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂	150	61	C : 64.00 H : 4.72	64.43 4.69
S-Benzyliso-N-p-chlorophenyl-TT	3-p-Chlorophenyl-imino-5-benzyl-D.	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	201	51	N : 8.85 S : 20.33	8.79 20.09
S-Benzyliso-N-p-methoxyphenyl-TT	3-p-methoxyphenyl-imino-5-benzyl-D.	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ O	152	63	N : 8.79 S : 20.54	8.91 20.38
S-Benzyliso-N-m-chlorophenyl-TT	3-m-Chlorophenylimino-5-benzyl-D-	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	207	53	N : 8.82 S : 20.12	8.79 20.09
S-Benzyliso-N-benzyl-TT	3-benzylimino-5-benzyl-D	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂	130	57	C : 64.46 H : 4.72	64.43 4.69

TT — denotes — Thiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamide.
D — denotes — 1,2,4-dithiazole.

(ii) Oxidation of N-arylthiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamides with bromine in dilute ethanol :

Compounds (III) were oxidised with bromine in dilute ethanol solution. On addition of ether hydrobromides of the respective dithiazoles got precipitated. On basification with ammonia, free bases were obtained which were crystallised from ethanol. These compounds were found to be identical with the respective 3-arylimino-5-benzyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles recorded in Table 2. The identity was confirmed from undepressed mixture melting points and superimposable IR spectra.

N-Arylthiocarbamoylphenylthioacetamides (III) :

(i) Reductive debenzoylation of S-benzyliso-N-arylthiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamides :

The desired S-benzyliso-N-arylthiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamide was dissolved in a mixture of pyridine-triethylamine (6:1) and a stream of dry hydrogen sulphide passed for 2 hr. The reaction mixture on pouring over crushed ice and subsequent acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid afforded the related N-arylthiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamide which was filtered out and crystallised from ethanol. The results are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—N-ARYLTHIOCARBAMOYL-PHENYLTHIOACETAMIDES (III)

Reactants	N-arylthiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamide formed.	Formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Analysis		ν max cm ⁻¹
					Found	Reqd.	
S-Benzyliso-N-phenyl-TT	N-phenyl-TT	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂	142	70	C : 63.40 H : 4.96	62.94 4.89	3200(m), 1600(w), 1555(m), 1480(m), 1370(w), 1245(m), 1160(w), 1080(m), 1040(w)
S-Benzyliso-N-p-tolyl-TT	N-p-tolyl-TT	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂	164	73	N : 9.52 S : 21.35	9.33 21.33	3250(m), 1605(w), 1550(m), 1485(m), 1365(m), 1245(m), 1165(vw), 1080(w), 1020(vw).
S-Benzyliso-N-p-chlorophenyl-TT	N-p-Chlorophenyl-TT	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	75	65	N : 8.94 S : 19.53	8.73 19.97	
S-Benzyliso-N-p-methoxyphenyl-TT	N-p-methoxyphenyl-TT	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O	182	71	N : 8.92 S : 20.47	8.86 20.25	3250(m), 1600(w), 1535(m), 1480(m), 1350(w), 1240(m), 1150(w), 1070(m), 1000(v).
S-Benzyliso-N-m-chlorophenyl-TT	N-m-chlorophenyl-TT	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	110	62	N : 8.76 S : 20.02	8.73 19.97	
S-Benzyliso-N-benzyl-TT	N-benzyl-TT	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂	140	69	C : 64.37 H : 5.36	64.00 5.33	

TT denotes — Thiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamide.

- (ii) *Reduction of 3-arylimino-5-benzyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles with hydrogen sulphide in pyridine-triethylamine solution :*

The related dithiazoles were reduced in a mixture of pyridinetriethylamine by passing hydrogen sulphide for about one hour. On cooling and acidification with dil. hydrochloric acid, the expected N-arylthiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamides (III) were obtained which were crystallised from ethanol. The identity of each product was established by mixture melting point with the authentic sample obtained by the conventional reduction of the S-benzyliso-N-arylthiocarbamoyl-phenylthioacetamide and also by identical i r spectra.

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